

A Comprehensive Study of Uterine Lesions in Hysterectomy Specimens: Clinical, Radiological, and Histopathological Insights

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Abstract:

Introduction: Hysterectomy is the most commonly performed gynecological surgery throughout the world as it provides definitive cure to a wide range of gynecological diseases, both benign and malignant. This study was undertaken to identify the most common uterine pathologies in hysterectomy specimens, to study the occurrence of lesions in relation to age and parity and to study association between histopathological features and clinical presentation of uterine lesions.

Methodology: This was retrospective and prospective observational study carried out over a period of one and half year from 1st July 2017 to 31st December 2018 in the pathology department and three hundred seven hysterectomy specimens were studied. The clinical history of all cases was collected from records. The specimens were processed using routine paraffin tissue processing methods and sections were stained with hematoxylin and eosin. Pathological findings in the uterus were noted.

Results: In the present study, 56.35% cases had undergone total hysterectomy, commonest age group was 41-50 years (43.00%) & multiparous were commonest. Menorrhagia (37.46%) followed by something coming out per vaginum(30.94%) were the most frequent clinical presentation. Histopathologically, the commonest endometrial findings were proliferative phase (37.46%) followed by atrophium endometrium (27.04%) and myometrial findings were leiomyoma(43.32%) followed by adenomyosis(28.01), both were commonly seen in 41-50 years. Leiomyomas were commonly seen at the intramural locations and showed hyalinization.

Conclusion: Hysterectomy is an effective treatment for various uterine pathologies. The study highlights the significance of histopathological examination for accurate diagnosis and management, even in grossly normal specimens. Clinical and radiological evaluations alone may not adequately diagnose conditions such as adenomyosis or early-stage malignancies.

Keywords: Hysterectomy, Histopathology, Proliferative phase, Leiomyoma.

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Introduction

Uterus, a vital reproductive organ is subjected to many benign and malignant disorders[4,10,12]. Most common clinical presenting features are per vaginal bleeding, vaginal discharge, pain in abdomen, menstrual irregularity, difficulty in micturition, postmenopausal bleeding and sensation of something coming out per vaginum[1]. Women worldwide suffer from gynecologic and obstetric disorders. Many treatment options are available including medical and conservative management, but hysterectomy still remains the most common gynecological procedure performed worldwide [6,8,10,12].

Hysterectomy is the definitive treatment for many pelvic pathologies which include leiomyoma, dysfunctional uterine bleeding, uterovaginal prolapse,

endometriosis, adenomyosis, pelvic inflammatory disease, chronic pelvic pain, gynecological cancers and obstetric complications[3,7,9,10,11]. Histological examination of hysterectomy specimens carries diagnostic, therapeutic and prognostic significance[2,8].

Hysterectomy may be total/complete –removal of the body, fundus, and cervix of the uterus or partial /subtotal/ supracervical hysterectomy - removal of the uterine body while leaving the cervix intact². When along with total hysterectomy, unilateral/bilateral adnexae are removed it is called as total hysterectomy with unilateral/ bilateral salpingoophorectomy(BSO)[3] and when along with total hysterectomy unilateral/bilateral fallopian

tubes are removed it is called as total hysterectomy with unilateral/bilateral salpingectomy.

Materials and Methods

This is a retrospective and prospective observational study of one and half year duration from 1st July 2017 to 31st December 2018 during which 300 cases were studied. There clinical data (age, clinical presentation, radiologic findings and other available investigations), gross findings were obtained from the surgical histopathological record section of the institute. Inclusion criteria were all the hysterectomy specimen received in the surgical histopathology section and age distribution from 20 years to 80 years. Exclusion criteria were cervical lesions, ovarian lesions, fallopian tube lesions, endometrial biopsy, cervical biopsy, myomectomy specimen, obstetric hysterectomy specimen, poor and unfixed specimen. In the retrospective period,

formalin fixed paraffin embedded tissue sections stained with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) were retrieved and reviewed. In the prospective period, the hysterectomy specimens were received in 10% formalin in the surgical histopathology section and were studied by routine paraffin tissue processing method. 3-5 micron thick sections were made from paraffin embedded blocks and slides were stained with hematoxylin and eosin stain. All sections of uterus were examined for various pathologies.

Results

In the present study, out of 307 hysterectomy cases, 56.35% (173 cases) had undergone total hysterectomy. The commonest age group involved was 41-50 years (43.00%), mean age was 47.35 years and median age was 45 years. Multiparous - 91.53% (281 cases) were the commonest (As shown in table1).

Table 1: Types of hysterectomy, Age-wise distribution, Parity distribution:

Sr.No.	Types of Hysterectomy (n = 307)	No. of cases	Percent (%)
1.	Total hysterectomy	173	56.35 %
2.	Subtotal hysterectomy	01	00.33 %
3.	Total hysterectomy with salpingectomy (uni/bilateral)	68	22.15 %
4.	Total hysterectomy with salpingoopherectomy (uni/bilateral)	65	21.17 %
Sr.No	Age Group (Years) (n = 307)	No. of cases	Percent (%)
1.	21-30	06	01.95 %
2.	31-40	78	25.40 %
3.	41-50	132	43.00 %
4.	51-60	52	16.94 %
5.	61-70	36	11.73 %
6.	71-80	03	00.98 %
Sr.No	Parity (n = 307)	No. of cases	Percent (%)
1.	Nulliparous	07	02.28%
2.	Primiparous	19	06.19%
3.	Multiparous	281	91.53 %

Table 2: Distribution of Clinical Presentation:

Sr. No.	Clinical Presentation	No.	Percent (%)
1.	Menorrhagia	115	37.46 %
2.	Something coming out PV	95	30.94 %
3.	Lower abdominal pain	76	24.75 %
4.	Dysmenorrhea	48	15.64 %
5.	Polymenorrhagia	24	07.82%
6.	Increased frequency of urination	20	06.51%
7.	Vaginal discharge	19	06.19%
8.	PV bleeding	19	06.19 %
9.	Postmenopausal bleeding	12	03.91%
10.	Metrorrhagia	05	01.63%

Menorrhagia was the commonest presentation (37.46%), followed by something coming out per vaginum (30.94%) (As shown in table 2). The commonest histopathological findings of endome-

trium were proliferative phase in 37.46% (115 cases), followed by atrophic endometrium in 27.04% (83 cases) and of myometrium were Leiomyoma in

43.32% (133 cases), followed by adenomyosis in 28.01% (86 cases) (As shown in 3 & 4).

Table 3: Histopathological findings of endometrium

Sr.No.	Endometrium (n = 307)		
	Histopathological findings	No. of cases	Percent (%)
1.	Proliferative phase	115	37.46 %
2.	Secretory phase	44	14.33 %
3.	Disordered proliferation	12	03.91%
4.	Pill effect	8	02.61 %
5.	Atrophic	83	27.04 %
6.	Acute endometritis	01	00.33 %
7.	Chronic endometritis	04	01.30 %
8.	Benign endometrial polyp	26	08.47 %
9.	Leiomyomatous polyp	04	01.30 %
10.	Endometrial adenomyomatous polyp	04	01.30%
11.	Nonatypical hyperplasia	04	01.30 %
12.	Endometrial adenocarcinoma	02	00.65 %

Fig 1: (a) Endometrium - proliferative phase. The glands are round to oval lined by pseudostratified epithelium. (b) Endometrium – secretory phase. The glands are tortuous, elongated and shows prominent subnuclear vacuoles and secretions. (c) Endometrium – pill endometrium showing pseudodecidualized stroma.

Fig 2: (a) Endometrium – acute endometritis showing neutrophilic infiltrate in glandular epithelium and lumen. (b) High power image of acute endometritis. (c) Endometrium – chronic follicular endometritis.

Fig 3: (a) Uterus with cervix – cut section shows endometrial polyp with tiny well circumscribed fibroid. (b) Endometrium – endometrial polyp showing dilated glands in a fibrotic stroma with thick walled blood vessels. (c) High power image polyp shows thick walled blood vessels. (d) Shows endometrial adenomyomatous polyp. (e) Shows submucosal leiomyomatous polyp. (f) Endometrium – atrophic showing cystically dilated glands with flattened epithelium.

Fig 4: (a) Endometrial hyperplasia: Uterus with cervix shows elongation of cervix with increased endometrial thickness measuring 1.5 cm. Endometrium is gray white, irregular, soft to firm. (b) Endometrial hyperplasia (nonatypical) - showing increase in the glands to stroma ratio and back to back arrangement of glands. (c) High power image shows tubular glands lined by pseudostratified epithelium.

Table 4: Histopathological findings of myometrium:

Sr. No.	Myometrium (n = 307)		
	Histopathological findings	No. of cases	Percent (%)
1.	Leiomyoma	100	32.57 %
2.	Adenomyosis	53	17.26 %
3.	Leiomyoma + Adenomyosis	33	10.75 %
4.	Adenomyoma	4	01.30 %
5.	Leiomyosarcoma	1	00.33 %
6.	Normal findings in myometrium	116	37.79 %

The commonest age group involved in leiomyoma and adenomyosis was 41-50 years in 55.64% (74 cases) & 55.81% (48 cases) respectively (As shown in table 5). Intramural was commonest site in 54.89% (73 cases) & hyalinization was the commonest secondary change in 36.09% (48 cases) of leiomyoma. The histological variant like cellular

leiomyoma, neurilemmoma & lipoleiomyoma were seen. 69.77% (60 cases) of superficial adenomyosis were seen (As shown in table 6). The association of radiohistopathological examination findings of uterine fibroid were seen in 98 cases of endometrial polyp seen in 3 cases and for adenomyosis were seen in 9 cases (As shown in table 7).

Fig 5: (a) Uterus with cervix - cut section shows polypoidal greyish white irregular mass extending into myometrium with areas of necrosis. (b) Endometrium – endometrial adenocarcinoma showing complex, papillary, tubular arrangement of glands. (c) High power image showing nuclear pleomorphism and hyperchromasia.

Table 5: Age-wise distribution of Leiomyoma & Adenomyosis:

Sr. No	Age group (years)	Leiomyoma (n =133)		Adenomyosis (n = 86)	
		No. of cases	Percent (%)	No. of cases	Percent (%)
1.	21-30	02	01.50%	02	02.32%
2.	31-40	33	24.81%	20	23.26%
3.	41-50	74	55.64%	48	55.81%
4.	51-60	19	14.29%	13	15.12%
5.	61-70	05	03.76%	03	03.49%
6.	71-80	00	00.00%	00	00.00%

Table 6: Leiomyoma - site wise distribution(n=133), Secondary changes & histological types of leiomyoma (n=133) and Adenomyosis with subtypes (n=86):

Sr.No	Leiomyoma with site wise distribution	No of cases	Percent(%)
1.	Subserosal	22	16.54 %
2.	Intramural	73	54.89 %
3.	Submucosal	09	06.77 %
4.	Subserosal+Intramural	21	15.79 %
5.	Subserosal+Submucosal	01	00.75 %
6.	Intramural+Submucosal	03	02.26 %
7.	Subserosal+Intramural+Submucosal	04	03.00 %

Sr.No.	Leiomyoma with/without secondary changes and histological variants	No of cases	Percent(%)
A	With secondary changes and histological variants	60	45.11 %
1.	Hyaline change	48	36.09 %
2.	Hyaline and myxoid change	01	00.75 %
3.	Hyaline change and calcification	01	00.75 %
4.	Hyaline change and red degeneration	01	00.75 %
5.	Hyaline change and neurilemmoma variant	02	01.50 %
6.	Cellular Leiomyoma	04	03.01 %
7.	Cellular leiomyoma with hyaline change and red degeneration	01	00.75 %
8.	Neurilemmoma variant of Leiomyoma	01	00.75 %
9.	Lipoleiomyoma	01	00.75 %
B	Without secondary changes and histological variants	73	54.89 %
Sr. No	Adenomyosis with subtypes	No. of cases	Percent (%)
1.	Superficial adenomyosis	60	69.77 %
2.	Superficial and deep adenomyosis	26	30.23 %

Fig 6: (a) Uterus with cervix with bilateral fallopian tube and ovary with multiple fibroids. (b) Uterus with cervix with unilateral fallopian tube and ovary shows large fibroid and separately sent nodular fibroid (c) Presence of single large intramural fibroid which is well circumscribed, gray white, firm in consistency with whorled appearance. (d) Shows single submucosal fibroid. (e) Shows multiple fibroids. (f) Shows separately sent fibroid.

Fig 7: (a) Myometrium – leiomyoma showing interlacing fascicles and whorling of smooth muscle cells. (b) High power image of leiomyoma showing spindle shaped cells with round to oval to cigar shaped bland nuclei. (c & d) Leiomyoma with secondary changes. (c) Leiomyoma with hyaline change & (d) Leiomyoma with features of red degeneration.

Fig 8: (a,b,c,d) Leiomyoma with histological variants - (a) Cellular leiomyoma showing increased cellularity & (b) High power image showing bland nuclear features. (c) Lipoleiomyoma showing clusters of adipocytes into the intervening stroma. (d) Leiomyoma with neurilemmoma variant.

Fig 9: (a) Myometrium– leiomyosarcoma showing increased cellularity. (b) leiomyosarcoma showing tumor necrosis. (c) High power image of leiomyosarcoma showing pleomorphic, hyperchromatic nuclei and mitotic figures.

Fig 10: (a,b) Adenomyosis, (a) Grossly, cut section shows multiple slit like spaces. b) Microscopy, showing endometrial glands and stroma within the myometrium. (c,d) Adenomyoma, (c) Uterus with cervix with separately sent mass shows features of adenomyoma. (d) Adenomyoma showing circumscribed nodular aggregate of endometrial glands, stroma and proliferation of smooth muscles within myometrium.

Table 7: Comparison of USG findings of uterine fibroid, endometrial polyp and adenomyosis with histopathological findings:

On Ultrasonography	Histopathological findings			P value
Uterine fibroid	Present	Absent	Total	< 0.05 Significant
Present	98	26	124	
Absent	35	148	183	
Total	133	174	307	
Endometrial polyp	Present	Absent	Total	
Present	03	02	05	
Absent	31	271	302	
Total	34	273	307	
Adenomyosis	Present	Absent	Total	
Present	09	03	12	
Absent	77	218	295	
Total	86	221	307	

Discussion

In the present study, the commonest age group involved was 41-50 years in 43.00% cases, which is in concordance with study of Ticku et al.[3] study (41.76%) and is comparable with Maheshwari J et al⁽²⁾(50.22%), Kaur et al.[7] studies (51.00%) but it shows higher percentage in their studies. Second most common age group involved was 31-40 years in 25.40% cases, which is in concordance with Maheshwari J et al.[2] (25.11%), Kaur et al.[7] studies (25.50%). Menorrhagia was the commonest clinical presentation in 37.46%, followed by something coming out per vaginum in 30.94% and vaginal discharge in 06.19% which are in concordance with Kaur et al. [7] study. i.e. (38.00%, 29.00% and 06.50% respectively).

Proliferative phase was the commonest endometrial histopathological finding in 37.46% cases, which is in concordance with Ticku et al.[3] (38.36%), Kaur et al.[7] (31.00%) studies and is in discordance with Fatehpuriya DS et al.[4], Verma D et al.[11] studies (83.90% & 53.00% respectively) due to high percentage of endometrial lesions but the commonest endometrial histopathological findings in their studies is proliferative phase of endometrium. The second most common endometrial finding was atrophic endometrium in 27.04% cases, which is comparable with Gangadharan V et al.[5] study (24.50%). Other endometrial findings were secretory phase in 14.33% cases, which is in concordance with Kaur et al.[7] study i.e. (13.00%). Acute endometritis and chronic endometritis were seen in 00.33% and 1.30% cases respectively, which are in concordance with Ticku et al.[3] (00.25% & 1.48% respectively). Endometrial adenocarcinoma was seen in 00.65% cases, which is in concordance with Gangadharan V et al.[5] study. i.e.(00.60%).

Leiomyoma was the commonest myometrial histopathological finding in 43.32% cases, which is in concordance with Tiwana KK et al.[9] (43.70%), Maheshwari J et al.[2] (42.30%), Gangadharan V et al.[5] (41.00%) studies. It is in discordance with Gattu V et al.[6] (60.00%), Fatehpuriya DS et al.[4] (58.80%), Kaur et al.[7] (65.00%) studies due to higher percentage and with Verma D et al.[11] (25.60%) study due to lower percentage of Leiomyoma. Intramural location of leiomyoma was the commonest finding in 54.89% which is comparable with Kaur et al.[7] study i.e.(62.90%). Lipoleiomyoma was seen in 00.75% which is in concordance with Gattu V et al.[6] study. i.e (00.50%). The most common secondary change noted was hyalinization in 36.09%, which is comparable with Kaur et al.[7] study i.e.(33.30%). Leiomyoma and adenomyosis were commonly seen in the age group of 41-50 years in 55.64% and 55.81% cases respectively, which are comparable with Ticku et al.[3] study i.e.(49.64% & 46.58%).

In the present study, p-value is significant for histopathological examination of leiomyoma, endometrial polyp and adenomyosis than radiological examination. The laboratory investigations were analyzed in all the hysterectomy cases and were within normal limits.

Conclusion

Hysterectomy remains the widely used treatment modality for various uterine pathologies. The present study was undertaken to evaluate the various histopathological spectrum of uterine lesions, their commonest age group distribution, clinical and radiological features. A clinicopathological correlation is necessary for proper interpretation of the diagnosis. This was done in our study, where clinical findings were correlated with the histopathological findings. Clinical history including age, presentation, radiological findings, laboratory investigations, gross examinations and microscopic examinations were properly studied. The commonest histopathological finding in endometrium is proliferative phase and leiomyoma in myometrium with the commonest site being Intramural. The most common age group is 41-50 years in which hysterectomy were done. Menorrhagia was the commonest clinical presentation. The most common indication for hysterectomy in our setting is excessive uterine bleeding. Leiomyoma was the most common histopathological finding for which hysterectomy was performed. Clinical examination and radiological evaluation may diagnose the fibroid uterus, polyps, prolapsed uterus and related complications. But abnormal excessive uterine bleeding due adenomyosis, endometritis, hyperplasia, early stages of malignant uterine lesions are quite difficult to diagnose clinicoradiologically and were confirmed by histopathological examination.

Hence, it is mandatory that every hysterectomy specimen, even if it has grossly appeared to be normal, should be subjected to detailed histopathological examination. So histopathological examination is mandatory for confirming the diagnosis and thus ensuring the proper management.

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